

Nuclear Quadrupole Resonance Studies on some Donor-Acceptor Type Complexes†

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A Townes and Dailey's analysis was carried out on the nqr data published so far by the author with some unpublished ones and also on some other existing literature data reported earlier. The results tally with the theoretical interpretation in many cases. The discrepancy observed in some cases may be due to higher multipolar interactions.

ELECTRON donor-acceptor type complexes show significant nqr frequency shift with respect to the frequency of the initial component molecules having the same probe. Direct connection between nqr coupling constant and charge distribution leads to the expectation that nqr should be a sensitive device for the study of inter-molecular charge transfer in solid state.

Weiss's suggestion¹ that nqr frequency should shift due to molecular complex formation through charge transfer interaction has been well demonstrated with molecules having quadrupolar nucleus either in acceptors or in donors or in both the donors and acceptors at the same time²⁻⁶. As expected, a linear relation between nqr shift and the charge transfer interaction energy $h\nu_{op}$ or the ionisation energy of the donor was obtained in all these cases. However, Maksyutin⁹ while studying the interaction of picryl chloride with substituted aromatic hydrocarbons proposed from theoretical consideration that if ³⁵Cl be on the donor molecule, $\Delta\nu$ should be negative and if ³⁵Cl be on the acceptor molecule $\Delta\nu$ should be positive, although his experimental results even do not always follow his proposition. The present author³⁻⁴ also showed in earlier communications that although a linear relation between the nqr shift ($\Delta\nu$) and the donor ionisation potential or $h\nu_{op}$ was obtained in all cases, Maksyutin's idea of negative shift with respect to donor or positive shift with respect to acceptor was not always corroborated with. However, according to Maksyutin, geometrical factors would also be of significant importance for the nqr shift in case of disubstituted-benzenes. According to Douglass¹⁰, the crystal field effect frequently shift quadrupole resonance frequencies by ± 200 kHz. In order to determine any shift arising from charge transfer, these crystal field effect as well as geometrical factors would have to be eliminated. Unfortunately, these extraneous effects are not obtainable at present either from experiments or calculations. Although electronic factor possesses a systematic

character, the other two factors, namely, geometrical factors and crystal field effect to a certain degree possess an accidental character, hence superposition of all these factors leads to the absence of any definite regularity in the nqr frequency shifts.

Frequency changes in these molecular complexes may be due primarily to change in electron density in the π - and σ -orbitals of the Cl atom. Maksyutin's analysis takes into account only π -orbital changes. However, in most cases it is the ³⁵Cl nqr signal that has been recorded when Cl atom is introduced as a substituent in the donor or acceptor. In these compounds, charge transfer takes place between the π -molecular orbital of the donor and acceptor, and the Cl atom does not participate in the electron exchange directly, the only effect that the electron transfer can have is on the nature of the character of the C-Cl bond. So in all probability, frequency changes would have contribution from the changes in electron density of σ -orbitals of the Cl atom as well. With this contention, we have calculated the change in ionicity of the C-Cl bond present in the donor or acceptor or in both following Townes and Dailey, with the nqr frequency reported earlier by the present author as well as by others.

Theory :

Townes and Dailey's model¹¹ analyses the nqr signal in molecules in terms of field gradient at the quadrupolar nucleus. The covalency of C-Cl bond is calculated following Townes and Dailey theory by the relation,

$$\left(\frac{eq Q}{h}\right)_{exp} = (1-i) \left(\frac{eq Q}{h}\right)_{atom}$$

where, i is the ionic character of the bond and therefore $(1-i)$ is the covalent character of the bond, $(eq Q/h)_{atom}$ is the nqr frequency for the atomic chlorine which is 109.7 MHz. In resonance terms following Townes and Dailey, bonding in these complexes may be described as a hybrid of a

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pure covalent bond and a pure ionic bond,

$$Q = (1 - i)(R - Cl) + i(R^+ - Cl^-)$$

where, *i* is the fractional ionic character of the bond. Calculation of *i*, therefore, amounts to estimating the extent of electron density change of Cl atom in a R-Cl bond.

Results and Discussion

We have calculated the ionicity of R-Cl bond of a large number of molecular complexes. The results are shown in Table 1. The nqr frequency change and ionicity of C-Cl bond in molecular complexes of *p*-chloronitrobenzene and *o*-chloronitrobenzene with different hydrocarbons are reported in the 8th International Symposium on NQR held at Darmstadt, Germany.

From Table 1 it may be observed that the ionicity of the C-Cl bond changes appreciably as it enters into complexation. Townes and Dailey's analysis suggests that the dipole moment of the C-Cl bond in the donor molecule will increase and that in the acceptor decrease on charge transfer complex formation. As expected, the data for chloranilic acid, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride and chloranil (acceptors) show that the ionicity decreases as these go into complexation. Same is true for *p*-dichlorobenzene, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-chlorophenol, the ionicity increases as they go for complexation with DDQ, chloranil, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride, chloranilic acid and *p*-chloronitrobenzene as donors, whereas a few others show opposite effect. Thus, a perfect generality cannot be claimed. The discrepancy may arise due to the presence of dipolar and multipolar interaction in

TABLE 1—IONICITIES OF DONORS, ACCEPTORS AND THE ELECTRON DONOR-ACCEPTOR COMPLEXES

Acceptors	Donors	Ionicity of the C-Cl bond in the complex from nqr data
Chloranilic acid ionicity = 0.6554	Benzene	0.6547
	Naphthalene	0.6543
	Triphenylene	0.6528
	Pyrene	0.6522
	Anthracene	0.6512
Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride ionicity = 0.6552	Benzene	0.6541
	Naphthalene	0.6534
	Pyrene	0.6499
	Anthracene	0.6489
Chloranil ionicity = 0.6591	Benzene	0.6566
	Naphthalene	0.6559
	Triphenylene	0.6528
	Pyrene	0.6528
	Anthracene	0.6512
<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene ionicity = 0.6639	Naphthalene	0.6606
	Anthracene	0.6582
	Pyrene	0.6589
	Chrysene	0.6596
	Biphenyl	0.6624
<i>o</i> -Chloronitrobenzene ionicity = 0.6667	Naphthalene	0.6639
	Anthracene	0.6589
	Chrysene	0.6617
	Biphenyl	0.6660
Picryl chloride ionicity = 0.6410	Benzene	0.6392
	Fluorobenzene	0.6383
	Chlorobenzene	0.6358
	Bromobenzene	0.6354
	Toluene	0.6347 (anti.)
		0.6388 (syn.)
	Iodobenzene	0.6331
	Phenol	0.6304
	Nitrobenzene	0.6402
	<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.6406
	<i>p</i> -Iodotoluene	0.6406
	<i>p</i> -Cresol	0.6399
	<i>p</i> -Bromotoluene	0.6390
	<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene	0.6340 (anti.)
		0.6362 (syn.)
		0.6324 } (³⁵ Cl <i>p</i> -chloro-
		0.6337 } toluene)
	<i>p</i> -Fluorotoluene	0.6350
	Mesitylene	0.6318
	Darene	0.6356
	Pentamethylbenzene	0.6330
Naphthalene	0.6360	
Anthracene	0.6372	
Phenanthrene	0.6361	

(Table 1 contd.)

		Donor	Acceptors
<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene ionicity = 0.6818	DDQ	0.6840	0.6513
	Chloranil ionicity = 0.6591	0.6871	0.6567
	Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride ionicity = 0.6552	0.6909	0.6620
	Chloranilic acid ionicity = 0.6554	0.6917	0.6627
	<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene ionicity = 0.6639	0.6904	0.6749
	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline ionicity = 0.6896	DDQ	0.6901
Chloranil ionicity = 0.6591		0.6917	0.6566
Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride ionicity = 0.6552		0.6970	0.6548
Chloranilic acid ionicity = 0.6554		0.6976	0.6591
<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene ionicity = 0.6639		0.6991	0.6704
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol ionicity = 0.6813		DDQ	0.6838
	Chloranil ionicity = 0.6591	0.6852	0.6548
	Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride ionicity = 0.6552	0.6886	0.6566
	Chloranilic acid ionicity = 0.6554	0.6898	0.6585
	<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene ionicity = 0.6639	0.6905	0.6715

the crystals of charge transfer complexes. This will considerably affect the bond character of C-Cl bond because of the change in potential gradient at Cl atom. This arises also from dipole-induced dipole interaction. Also, while calculating, the dipole moment geometry of the complexes should play a dominant role as well.

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